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ABSTRACT

This document focuses on the design of a dogleg between a plasma injector in the energy range of 200-300 MeV and a second plasma stage reaccelerating the plasma in the multi-GeV scale. The framework at CILEX facility and the constraints to enable a two-stage laser-plasma acceleration will be described. A status of the optics of the transfer line, on the tolerances, of the magnetic design, and of the diagnostics will be given. The next steps to make such a transfer line work will be discussed.

ARIES Consortium, 2018

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Executive summary

When designing Laser wakefield accelerators (LWFA) for very high energies, a multi-stage approach has to be adopted because of particle dephasing and energy depletion. Hence the need for an interstage electron beam transfer line that preserves the particular beam quality. The design of a stigmatic, achromatic and isochronous beam line corresponding to this requirement is presented here.

Firstly, the optics of the line is described. The considered initial conditions and constraints are explained. The method of optimization of the set-up is discussed and implemented in simulations. A baseline for the transfer line is proposed with parameters for all magnets. Magnet parameters are within reach of current state of the art for normal conducting or permanent magnet technology. The expected performances of the line are given. Tracking studies with an ad-hoc initial electron beam distribution have been performed. Results show that only a small part of the final beam distribution is within the specifications (transverse position and time slot). Nevertheless, the initial beam distribution comes from first plasma simulations. There is still room for improvement of the plasma injector. Authors are confident in better results if the plasma density profile in the first stage can be optimized.

Secondly, the sensitivity of the transfer line to errors (misalignment and initial beam parameter deviations) has been investigated. Correction schemes have not been implemented yet. Therefore, only the impact of errors which cannot be corrected (because their characteristic time is short compared to the repetition time of one minute) is addressed. First studies show that the line is very sensitive. Transverse displacement of only a few micrometres is allowed for the quadrupoles and is the most demanding parameter. Nevertheless, more studies are needed to refine the tolerance study for the transfer line.

Design of the magnets has been addressed. The main effort was put on the first permanent dipole. Indeed, the possibility to use a permanent dipole initially designed solely for the electron spectrometer of the CILEX facility is discussed. For a reference energy of the electron beam fixed at 300 MeV, the use of such a dipole seems possible. Studies have also shown that all electromagnets are feasible if an inner diameter of 30 mm and a reference energy of 200 MeV are chosen. In the case of a reference energy of 300 MeV and an inner diameter of 40 mm, dipoles and sextupoles are feasible. A second iteration is necessary for the quadrupole because the saturation field is reached. Permanent quadrupoles have not been designed yet but are within state of the art and should not be a showstopper.

The next steps for the project are described. The baseline needs to be updated accordingly with advances on the magnet design. For instance, more realistic field maps will be used to take into account the field inhomogeneity in the permanent dipoles. The plasma injector and plasma accelerator will be improved through plasma simulation. When the second stage is better defined, the transfer line will be updated to fill the matching conditions. More studies will be performed to refine the tolerances on the line. Correction schemes will be implemented accordingly with used diagnostics. Monte Carlo studies will be undertaken to check the final performances of the line in presence of collimators. Permanent dipoles are in the final design stage. The inner diameter of the

beam pipe will be chosen soon. The design of the electromagnets will be then optimized and 3D calculations will be performed. As soon as the magnetic design is frozen, electromagnets will be ordered from industry to be delivered in 2019. The needs in diagnostics will be defined accordingly to the beam properties in the line. Specifications for the diagnostics will be validated through simulations. The total cost will be better evaluated.

1. Introduction

In laser-wakefield accelerators (LWFA) dephasing and beam-depletion make the use of multiple acceleration stages necessary in order to reach multi-GeV electron beams. Furthermore, on the low energy end, a first injection stage before subsequent acceleration allows to uncouple the injection mechanism from the acceleration and consequently a better tuning of the plasma structures. Such 2-stage acceleration experiment is being considered at the multi-petawatt laser facility CILEX [1], with transport of electrons from an all-optical injector in the non-linear (blowout) regime to a booster in the linear regime. The compact transport line has to be sufficiently achromatic, isochronous, and astigmatic which is a challenge at an energy around 200-300 MeV. In contrast to very compact interstage transport schemes, this project focuses on the control and characterization of the electron beam produced in the injector stage. The funding from ARIES covers only part of the full cost estimate. Complementary funding is provided through a national funding in the final stage of approval and extending on to 2020, and is labelled here as a direct contribution from CNRS/LULI, the lead beneficiary of this funding. The components of the transport line, if feasible, will be procured from industry, tested, characterized and integrated in the CILEX facility. The properties of the line will be measured.

This report covers the description of initial beam properties and the constraints the transfer line should fulfil. The method of optimization of the setup is discussed. Parameters of the baseline are described and final beam properties will be given. First, tolerance estimates on the beam fluctuation and on the misalignment error are provided. Then, the magnetic design of the magnets are covered to check the feasibility of the magnets.

2. Optics of the line

2.1 GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS

2.1.1 Coordinate set

Special care should be taken about the choice of the coordinate set. Indeed, different simulation codes were used in this study: MAD-X [2] for envelope and matrix calculations and TraceWIN [3] or elegant [4] for tracking calculations. The bottleneck is that the used basis for the coordinates is different. One particle of the beam is characterized in MAD-X by the 6D canonical coordinates $\left(x, \frac{p_x}{p_r}, y, \frac{p_y}{p_r}, l = -c(t - t_r), \frac{E - E_r}{p_r c}\right)$ whereas it is characterized in TraceWin and elegant by the coordinate set $\left(x, x' = \frac{dx}{ds}, y, y' = \frac{dy}{ds}, l, \delta = \frac{p - p_r}{p_r}\right)$ where x is the horizontal position, y the vertical one, E the total energy, p the total momentum, p_x the horizontal canonical momentum, p_y the vertical canonical momentum, x' the horizontal slope, y' the vertical slope, t the arrival time of the particle, c is the speed of light in vacuum. The index r refers to the reference particle. We will respectively use the indexes 0 and 1 to refer to the coordinates of one particle at the start and at the end of the transfer line. Let X_0 be the initial coordinates of one particle. The final coordinates X_1 will be given by the Taylor-Lagrange expansion:

$$\forall i = 1..6, X_{1,i} = \sum_{j=1}^6 R_{ij} X_{0,j} + \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{k=1}^6 T_{ijk} X_{0,j} X_{0,k} + \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{k=1}^6 \sum_{l=1}^6 U_{ijkl} X_{0,j} X_{0,k} X_{0,l} \quad (1)$$

Or in compact notation: $X_1 = R \cdot X_0 + T(X_0, X_0) + U(X_0, X_0, X_0) + o(X_0^3)$

The Σ matrix is the covariance matrix defined by $\Sigma = \overline{X \cdot X^T}$. Horizontal emittance ε is the square root of the determinant of Σ projected in the plane $\left(x, \frac{p_x}{p_r}\right)$ (phase-space emittance) or (x, x') (trace-space emittance). Relative emittance growth, given by the determinant of the Σ matrix, along the line for the horizontal plane (vertical plane is deduced by replacing indexes 1 and 2 by respectively 3 and 4) is given by [5]:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\varepsilon_1^2 - \varepsilon_0^2}{\varepsilon_0^2} \approx & [\gamma_1(2T_{1kl}T_{166} + 4T_{1k6}T_{1l6} + 6R_{1k}U_{1l66}) \\ & + \beta_1(2T_{2kl}T_{266} + 4T_{2k6}T_{2l6} + 6R_{2k}U_{2l66}) \\ & + 2\alpha_1(T_{1kl}T_{266} + T_{2kl}T_{166} + 4T_{1k6}T_{2l6} + 3R_{1k}U_{2l66} \\ & + 3R_{2k}U_{1l66})] \frac{\Sigma_{0,kl}}{\varepsilon_0} \Sigma_{0,66} + o(\Sigma_{0,66}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

with α, β and γ the Twiss parameters¹. Summation on repeated indexes is implied.

¹ Twiss parameters α, β and γ are defined as $\alpha = -\frac{\Sigma_{12}}{\varepsilon}, \beta = \frac{\Sigma_{11}}{\varepsilon}$, and $\gamma = \frac{\Sigma_{22}}{\varepsilon} = \frac{1+\alpha^2}{\beta}$ where ε is the beam emittance and Σ the covariance matrix of the beam distribution.

At first order, both coordinate sets are equivalent and matrix R stays unchanged. But at higher order they behave differently and some discrepancy on the nonlinear terms in T and U can appear. For instance, in the case of a drift of length L , $T_{126} = \frac{L}{2\beta_r}$ with MAD-X coordinates whereas $T_{126} = 0$ with elegant coordinates. In the case of a large initial divergence and momentum spread as with beams generated from laser-plasma injectors, the phase-space emittance increases in a drift whereas the trace-space emittance stays constant [6] [7] [8]. There is equality between both at a waist. In the following, transfer line was optimized with MAD-X coordinates.

2.1.2 Beam features

The goal of this transfer line is to transport an electron beam generated from a plasma injector in the (nonlinear) bubble regime in the energy range of 200-300 MeV to a second plasma stage to be reaccelerated. The CILEX facility hosting the transfer line is a multipurpose facility. The two laser-lines driving the injector and accelerator plasma stages have a lateral offset. This grants the possibility to use other plasma targets or not to send the electrons into the transfer line. That is why using a dogleg was decided: by switching off (or removing) the first dipole, the electron beam can go straight for other applications². Moreover, in this configuration, diagnostics can be used to study the spent laser's properties after interaction with the plasma. The transfer line should enable to characterize the electron beam and to match it to the second stage. The expected beam properties at the end of the first (injector) plasma stage are:

- Energy range: 200-300 MeV.
- Rms size: $\approx \mu\text{m}$.
- FWHM energy: \approx a few %.
- Total charge: \approx 10-100 pC.
- Rms angular divergence: a few mrad.
- No correlation between transverse and longitudinal planes.
- FWHM time length: \approx 10 fs.
- Peak current: \approx a few kA.
- Normalized emittance of 1 μm .

Since the beam transfer line is a dogleg, the presence of dipoles generates dispersion. To keep small final beam sizes, the dispersion should be zero at the entrance of the second plasma stage. That gives the conditions for the beam to be achromatic:

$$R_{16} = \frac{\partial x_1}{\partial \delta_0} = 0 \text{ and } R_{26} = \frac{\partial x'_1}{\partial \delta_0} = 0 \quad (3)$$

² “Dogleg” is a transfer line that contains a pair of equal and opposite strength dipole bends separated by a drift. This is used to realise a parallel displacement of the beam trajectory without changing its direction.

Moreover, the path length in the dipoles depends on the electron energy. Although the velocity spread is very small, a variation of the path length with energy lengthens the bunch. Therefore, the transfer line should be iso-chronous to first order with the constraints:

$$R_{56} = \frac{\partial l_1}{\partial \delta_0} = 0, R_{52} = \frac{\partial l_1}{\partial x'_{10}} = 0, \text{ and } R_{54} = \frac{\partial l_1}{\partial y'_{10}} = 0. \quad (4)$$

Another constraint is to minimize the sensitivity of the final conditions to the large fluctuations of the average electron beam angle commonly observed LWFA experiments. A solution is to impose the stigmatism conditions:

$$R_{12} = \frac{\partial x_1}{\partial x'_{10}} = 0 \text{ and } R_{34} = \frac{\partial y_1}{\partial y'_{10}} = 0. \quad (5)$$

Currently, the matching constraints of the beam to the second plasma stage are not fixed yet because the second plasma stage is not fully defined. Indeed, matching constraints depend on the choice of the plasma density and of the shape of the plasma ramp. In the absence of better choice, the constraint here is to get the same final beam size. Final quadrupoles will be adjusted to get needed matching conditions in a second step. More quadrupoles could be then needed. The constraint to keep final beam sizes near the initial beam sizes implies a magnification factor near 1:

$$|R_{11}| = \left| \frac{\partial x_1}{\partial x_0} \right| \approx 1 \text{ and } |R_{33}| = \left| \frac{\partial y_1}{\partial y_0} \right| \approx 1 \quad (6)$$

The challenges of such a transfer line are to get a final beam size of a few micrometers and a final bunch length of a few tens of femtoseconds despite nonlinear terms brought by the transfer line, misalignment and field errors, and collective effects like space charge.

2.1.3 Geometry of the line

The transfer line is to be installed in the experimental hall of CILEX facility. The constraints on the installation have imposed a transverse separation of 3 m between both plasma chambers whereas the longitudinal separation can be in the range from 6 to 9 m. This longitudinal separation is now fixed at 7.675 m for reasons described in the section 2.2.3. The geometry of the dogleg has been chosen to have a point of symmetry. Indeed, if we write R^M the transfer matrix between the start and the middle of the line, we get the relation:

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + 2R_{12}^M R_{21}^M & 2R_{12}^M R_{22}^M & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2R_{16}^M R_{22}^M \\ 2R_{11}^M R_{21}^M & 1 + 2R_{12}^M R_{21}^M & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2R_{16}^M R_{21}^M \\ 0 & 0 & 1 + 2R_{34}^M R_{43}^M & 2R_{34}^M R_{44}^M & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2R_{33}^M R_{43}^M & 1 + 2R_{34}^M R_{43}^M & 0 & 0 \\ 2R_{16}^M R_{21}^M & 2R_{16}^M R_{22}^M & 0 & 0 & 1 & 2(R_{16}^M R_{26}^M + R_{56}^M) \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

The conditions (3), (4), (5), and (6) are then equivalent to the following constraints:

$$R_{16}^M = 0, R_{56}^M = 0, R_{12}^M = 0 \text{ or } R_{22}^M = 0, R_{34}^M = 0 \text{ or } R_{44}^M = 0 \quad (8)$$

Moreover, if we choose the conditions $R_{16}^M = 0, R_{56}^M = 0, R_{22}^M = 0, R_{34}^M = 0$, symmetry gives the additional second-order relations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{116} &= 2R_{11}^M T_{226}^M \\
 T_{126} &= 2R_{12}^M T_{226}^M \\
 T_{136} &= 2R_{12}^M (T_{236}^M - R_{33}^M R_{43}^M T_{246}^M) \\
 T_{146} &= 0 \\
 T_{166} &= 0 \\
 T_{316} &= 2R_{44}^M (T_{316}^M + R_{11}^M R_{21}^M T_{326}^M) \\
 T_{326} &= 0 \\
 T_{336} &= 2R_{43}^M T_{346}^M \\
 T_{346} &= 2R_{44}^M T_{346}^M \\
 T_{366} &= 2R_{44}^M T_{366}^M \\
 T_{516} &= 2(R_{26}^M (T_{116}^M + R_{11}^M R_{21}^M T_{126}^M) + T_{516}^M + R_{11}^M R_{21}^M T_{526}^M) \\
 T_{526} &= 0 \\
 T_{536} &= 2R_{33}^M R_{43}^M (R_{26}^M T_{146}^M + T_{546}^M) \\
 T_{546} &= 2(R_{26}^M T_{146}^M + T_{546}^M) \\
 T_{566} &= 2(R_{26}^M T_{166}^M + T_{566}^M)
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

The use of sextupoles in the transfer line enables to cancel some second-order terms like T_{566} (to reduce the bunch lengthening) or T_{346}^M (to reduce the emittance growth in the vertical plane). It is worth to note that only one dipole family is not enough to cancel R_{56} . Indeed, R_{56} can be written under the form:

$$R_{56} = \int \left(\frac{1}{\gamma_r^2} - \frac{R_{16}(s)}{\rho} \right) ds \tag{10}$$

ρ is the curvature radius of the trajectory and γ_r the Lorentz factor of the reference particle. $\frac{R_{16}(s)}{\rho}$ is non zero only in the dipoles. Therefore, if only two dipoles are used to make the dogleg, $\frac{R_{16}(s)}{\rho}$ is always positive and R_{56} cannot be cancelled when γ_r becomes large. That is why a second dipole family is used. Geometry of the dogleg is given in Figure 1 and is similar to the transfer line of ARES-SINBAD [9]. The dogleg is made of a first doublet to capture the beam, of a first (strong) dipole to bend the trajectory, of a quadrupole to have some flexibility on the dispersion at the entrance of the second dipole (and thus to tune the value of R_{56}), of a first sextupole, of a second (weak) dipole (to enable the cancelation of R_{56}), of a second doublet to match the dispersion at the middle of the line, and of a second sextupole. The second part of the line is then symmetrized by keeping the same sign for the quadrupole gradients and by using the opposite sign for the dipoles and sextupoles.

Figure 1: Geometry of the dogleg. The dipoles are shown in blue, the quadrupoles in red and the sextupoles in green.

2.2 OPTIMIZATION OF THE LINE OPTICS

2.2.1 Framework

The transfer line is to be hosted at CILEX facility. The design of the interaction chamber implies a minimum distance between the end of the first dipole and the entrance of the next elements of about one meter. The first doublet and the first dipole will be located inside this vacuum chamber. They will be made of permanent magnets. Their inner aperture should allow the laser passing through. The other magnets will have a beam pipe and will be made of electromagnets. The parameter set used for this transfer line is given in Table 1. The next addressed question was how to optimize the magnet parameters to fill all constraints given in the previous section.

Table 1: Parameter set used for the optimization of the transfer line.

Longitudinal footprint	6000-9000	mm
Transverse footprint	3000	mm
Length of first dipole	550	mm
Length of second dipole	100	mm
Length of permanent quadrupoles	60	mm
Length of electromagnet quadrupoles	100	mm
Length of sextupoles	100	mm
Inter-distance between permanent magnets	40	mm
Inter-distance between electromagnets	50	mm
Distance between first and second dipoles	1300	mm
Distance plasma-first quadrupole	200	mm
Distance plasma-first dipole	425	mm

2.2.2 Method

To optimize the transfer line, a parametric approach was used. Indeed, thanks to the constraints on the layout and on the optics given by (8), only 4 degrees of freedom remain: longitudinal size of

the transfer line, distance L_{QD2} between the second dipole and the second doublet, value of the dispersion slope R_{26}^M at the middle of the line, and ratio r between the dispersion after and before the third quadrupole. A 4D grid has then been created. For each parameter set, magnet positions, dipole fields, quadrupole gradients, and sextupole gradients are calculated:

- The angles θ_1 and θ_2 of the dipoles (and thus their fields B_1 and B_2) and the distance between the second dipole and the middle of the transfer line are calculated to get $R_{56}=0$ and the final coordinates of the transfer line in the laboratory frame (transverse and longitudinal positions).
- The gradient G_3 of the third quadrupole Q03 is adjusted to get the value of r .
- The gradients G_4 and G_5 of the fourth and fifth quadrupoles Q04 and Q05 are adjusted to get $R_{16}^M = 0$ and the target value of R_{26}^M at the middle of the transfer line.
- The gradients G_1 and G_2 of the first and second quadrupoles Q01 and Q02 are adjusted to get $R_{22}^M = 0$ and $R_{34}^M = 0$ at the middle of the transfer line.
- The gradients H_1 and H_2 of the first and second sextupoles SX1 and SX2 are adjusted to get $T_{566} = 0$ and $T_{346}^M = 0$.

The different parameter sets are then compared by the following figure of merit, which combines optics terms and certain magnet parameters.

$$f(X) = \left(\frac{R_{21}}{10}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{R_{43}}{10}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{T_{126}}{10}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{H_1}{100}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{H_2}{100}\right)^2, \quad (11)$$

The final choice is made under additional constraints, e.g. a limit on the maximum beta-function on the line.

2.2.3 Results

Amongst all explored geometries, the cases with a normalized strength in the sextupoles above 2000 m^{-3} (giving too large gradients) or values of R_{21} and R_{43} above 1000 m^{-1} (giving a transfer line too sensitive to misalignment errors) were excluded. The obtained figures of merit, quadrupole and sextupole gradients are summarized in Figure 2 for a longitudinal size of 6 meters and in Figure 3 for a longitudinal size of 9 meters. The variation of the dipole fields, of the quadrupole gradients, of the sextupole gradients, and of the optical terms as a function of the longitudinal size of the transfer line is given in Figure 4. As we can see, the variation of the quadrupole gradients is very small: only a few percent's on the whole variation range. We can also see that increasing the length of the transfer line reduces the size of the set containing the allowed values. On the other hand, lengthening the transfer line allows to reduce the dipole field (since the bending angle decreases) and thus to reduce the high-order dependence like T_{126} or the variation of the path length with energy (mainly brought on by dipoles). Another advantage is to reduce the maximum dispersion, and thus to increase the energy acceptance of the line. The longitudinal size was then fixed at 7.675 m, which is a good compromise between constraints from the existing site (some values in the range 6-9 m were excluded for technical reasons), reduction of the dipole field (and of the higher-order term) and small values of the optical terms R_{21} and R_{43} .

Figure 2: Values of the figure of merit (top left), gradients of the quadrupoles $Q01$ (top middle), $Q02$ (top right), $Q03$ (middle left), $Q04$ (middle), $Q05$ (middle right), and of the sextupoles $SX1$ (bottom left) and $SX2$ (bottom middle) in the case of a longitudinal size of 6 meters and a reference energy of 200 MeV. The selected optimum is shown by the red dot (bottom left of each plot).

Figure 3: Values of the figure of merit (top left), gradients of the quadrupoles QP1 (top middle), QP2 (top right), QP3 (middle left), QP4 (middle), QP5 (middle right), and of the sextupoles SX1 (bottom left) and SX2 (bottom middle) in the case of a longitudinal size of 9 meters and a reference energy of 200 MeV. The selected optimum is shown by the red dot.

Figure 4: Variation of the dipole fields (top left), quadrupole gradients (top right), of the sextupole gradients (bottom left), and of the optical terms (bottom right) as a function of the longitudinal length of the transfer line. The dashed line shows the values found for the baseline with a longitudinal length of $Z=7.675$ m.

2.3 BASELINE

2.3.1 Line parameters

The retained values after optimization are then a longitudinal size of 7.675 m, a value of $r=0$, a value of $R_{26}^M = -0.575$, and a distance of 100 mm between the second dipole and the second doublet. The found fields in the dipoles, quadrupoles and sextupoles are respectively summed up in Table 2, Table 3, and

Table 4 for reference energies of 200 MeV and 300 MeV. Currently, two options remain on the beam pipe diameter after the vacuum chamber: 30 mm (baseline) and 40 mm. The option of 30 mm allows to reduce the magnetic field in the coils and thus the dissipative power whereas the option of 40 mm helps to increase the energy acceptance of the transfer line. The resulting distances between elements are summed up in Table 1. The obtained survey layout of the transfer line is given in Figure 5. The two first quadrupoles (Q01 and Q02) and the first dipole D1 will be made of permanent quadrupoles and inserted into a vacuum chamber. Since the maximum dispersion in the transfer line is 0.84 m, the energy acceptance is expected to be $\pm 1.8\%$ (for a beam pipe diameter of 30 mm) or $\pm 2.7\%$ (for a beam pipe diameter of 40 mm).

TraceWin - CEA/DRF/Irfu/DACM

Figure 5: Survey layout of the transfer line. The dipoles are shown in blue, the quadrupoles in dark blue and the sextupoles in green.

Table 2: Dipole parameters in the baseline. The fields are calculated for reference energies of 200 MeV and 300 MeV.

Dipole	Length [mm]	Angle [rad]	Field [T]	Gap [mm]
D1	550	0.464	0.56/0.84	17
D2	100	-0.033	-0.22/-0.33	30/40

Table 3: Quadrupole parameters in the baseline. The gradients are calculated for reference energies of 200 MeV and 300 MeV.

Quadrupole	Length [mm]	Gradient [T/m]	Inner diameter [mm]
Q01	60	105/157.5	10
Q02	60	-73/109.5	10
Q03	100	-5/-7.5	30/40
Q04	100	20/30	30/40
Q05	100	-20/-30	30/40

Table 4: Sextupole parameters in the baseline. The gradient is defined here by the second derivative of the magnetic field with the position. Be careful: some other definitions include a factor $\frac{1}{2}$. The gradients are calculated for reference energies of 200 MeV and 300 MeV.

Sextupole	Length [mm]	Gradient [T/m ²]	Inner diameter [mm]
SX1	100	152/228	30/40
SX2	100	-116/-174	30/40

2.3.2 Tracking results

Currently, first simulations were performed with Smilei simulation software [10] to get an initial 6D distribution of an electron beam at the exit of the first plasma stage.

In this particular case, the Gaussian laser pulse of 7.5J^3 and FWHM duration of 20 fs and $0.8\ \mu\text{m}$ wavelength is focused on spot size of $w_0=40\ \mu\text{m}$ at the plasma entrance resulting in normalized vector potential $a_0=2.56$ in vacuum. The plasma has an electron density of $5.0\ 10^{18}\ \text{cm}^{-3}$ and a length of 1.55 mm including linear ramp of 0.1 mm at entrance and exit.

The electron bunch is defined in the simulation by all electrons having an energy within one FWHM of the peak energy $E=204\ \text{MeV}$. The overall bunch charge is 1 nC.

The electron bunch parameters at exit of the plasma are the following. The bunch longitudinal rms size is $4.9\ \mu\text{m}$ (16 fs) and transverse rms size of $2.5\ \mu\text{m}$. The average current of the bunch at plasma exit is of the order of 70 kA. The rms divergence is 17 mrad, the transverse normalized emittance is 7 mm.mrad and the rms energy spread is 15%.

In this simulation, the resulting electron distribution has a long low-energy-tail. However, these electrons will be lost anyway after the dipole. That is why, to speed up calculations, reasonable energy cuts were done on the initial distribution. Since the expected relative energy acceptance in first-order is $\pm 1.8\%$, the initial beam is cut at 200 MeV (peak energy) $\pm 10\ \text{MeV}$ (in other terms $\pm 5\%$). The distribution has then been sampled by 100,000 macroparticles, which is enough to get some characteristics of the beam like the centroid or the rms sizes. The 2D-projections of the used initial distribution in different planes are shown given in Figure 6. After the cuts, the angular rms divergence is as high 12 mrad since the downstream plasma density ramp has not been optimized. Recent studies have shown that a significant reduction of beam divergence can be reached by using an adiabatic ramp [11] or an exponential ramp [12]. This distribution can be considered first estimation of the beam behaviour in the transfer line but more studies are needed to assess the effects of possible improvements of the plasma injector. The final beam distribution is given in Figure 7 with a logarithmic colour scale. The beam tails are not negligible and a cut should be necessary to have a better accuracy on the determination of the centroids or of the beam sizes. A collimator with a diameter $\Phi = 8\ \text{mm}$ has then been added at the entrance of the quadrupole Q01 to cut the angles larger than 20 mrad. Vertical slits were added at the entrance of the quadrupole Q03 at the positions $x = \pm 4\ \text{mm}$ to cut in energy at $\pm 0.67\%$. The obtained final distribution with collimators is given in Figure 8 with a logarithmic colour scale after tracking with elegant. A clear improvement can be observed on the final beam quality. Measurement of the beam properties (like the centroid) will be more precise with collimators. In the following, the beam line is assumed to have these collimators inserted. The beam size, the beam emittance, and the bunch length along the line are given in Figure 9 and Figure 10. The emittance growth is not negligible despite collimation. Equation (2) explains this increase: the initial Twiss parameter $\gamma_{x,y}$ is very large: over

³ This energy corresponds to half of the maximum energy of the APOLLON F2 beam (diameter 140mm).

12000 m^{-1} . A reduction of this parameter by improving the plasma injector could help to cure this emittance increase.

Figure 6: Initial beam distribution in different planes. The colour gives the charge density with an arbitrary unit (logarithmic scale).

Figure 7: Final beam distribution in different planes. The colour gives the charge density with an arbitrary unit (logarithm scale).

Figure 8: Final beam distribution in different planes. The colour gives the charge density with an arbitrary unit (logarithm scale). A collimator of $\Phi = 8$ mm is added at the entrance of Q01 (giving a cut at ± 20 mrad). Slits at position $x = \pm 4$ mm are added at the exit of Q03 (equivalent to a cut at $\pm 0.67\%$ in energy).

Figure 9: Variation of the rms beam size and of the maximum amplitude (left, the right plot is a zoom on the y-axis of the left plot). A collimator of $\Phi = 8$ mm is added at the entrance of Q01 (giving a cut at ± 20 mrad). Slits at position $x = \pm 4$ mm are added at the exit of Q03 (giving a cut at $\pm 0.67\%$ in energy).

Figure 10: Variation of the normalized emittance (left) and of the bunch length (right). A collimator of $\Phi = 8$ mm is added at the entrance of Q01 (giving a cut at ± 20 mrad). Slits at position $x = \pm 4$ mm are added at the exit of Q03 (giving a cut at $\pm 0.67\%$ in energy).

3. Sensitivity of the line to errors

The design goal for the transfer line is an efficient transport of a beam generated by a plasma injector to a second plasma stage limiting as much as possible the growth of both bunch length and emittance. The reference design presented above fulfils the constraints (3), (4), (5), and (6). Nevertheless, some errors like misalignment generate errors on these final properties. The key point is to ensure that the final beam is in the 6D acceptance of the second stage to avoid injection losses in the second stage. The aim here is to quantify the impact of the misalignment and field errors on the beam transport. It is worth noting that in a second step some errors may be corrected but other may not. Only static errors like magnetization errors might be corrected. Indeed, with the maximum repetition rate of one laser shot per minute, feedback systems based on beam monitors cannot be used to correct dynamic errors on the beam (like ground vibrations, jitters, . . .). For instance, an error on the path length is critical only if it varies from shot to shot. Because of strongly populated distribution tails, quartiles were preferred to define beam sizes instead of rms sizes. In elegant, W_x/W_y corresponds to a 68.28% width in x/y (equivalent to the rms size for a Gaussian distribution). The 70% span was used to define the bunch length (the time width which contains 70% of the particles). By this way, results are less sensitive to the tail contributions.

To obtain a valid estimation of the tolerable errors, it is necessary – in principle – to assess their effect on the 6D acceptance of the second stage. An initial guess is to keep the beam centroid in the range of $\sigma_x = 10$ μm . The arrival time variation should be in the range of about $\sigma_t = 20$ fs (to maintain the electron beam synchronized with the second laser beam). If the error on the initial beam angle is assumed to be $\sigma_\theta = 1$ mrad and on the energy $\sigma_\delta = 0.5\%$, we should have:

$$|\Delta R_{12}| < \frac{\sigma_x}{\sigma_\theta} = 10 \text{ mm}, |\Delta R_{34}| < 10 \text{ mm}, |\Delta R_{56}| < \frac{\sigma_t c}{\sigma_\delta} = 0.12 \text{ mm}$$

The constraint on R_{56} is very strong and should be relaxed. In the following, the final centroid and beam sizes are calculated as a function of the applied error. Only errors on the dipoles and

quadrupoles or on the initial beam distribution (offset in position or in energy) are considered. In all cases, the initial distribution is the one used for tracking studies. Collimators are inserted in the line. A collimator of $\Phi=8$ mm is inserted at the entrance of Q01 (giving a cut at ± 20 mrad). Slits at position $x=\pm 4$ mm are added at the exit of Q03 (giving a cut at $\pm 0.67\%$ in energy). Each error is applied alone (for instance a horizontal misalignment of the quadrupole Q04).

3.1 INITIAL BEAM MISALIGNMENT

The final beam properties are determined for a horizontal/vertical position offset of DX/DY, a horizontal/vertical angle offset of DXP/DYP or a relative energy offset of DE applied to the initial beam. One should consider that with an energy spread greater than the energy offset, there will be electrons at the reference energy (and thus at $DE=0$). The sensitivity to DE gives an idea of the transmission of the transfer line as a function of energy. Figure 11 shows the obtained variations of the beam parameters $\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle, \langle t \rangle, w_x, w_y, \Delta t_{70}$ at the final point. We see that the variation of $\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle$ is driven by the initial DX/DY (as expected) but also by the initial DYP although the stigmatic condition is fulfilled. The beam size variation is also driven by errors on the initial angle. The reason of this behaviour comes from the non-negligible value of the third order term U_{3444} and of the large initial angular divergence. Indeed, if we take into account the variation of $\langle y \rangle$ with DYP, we can estimate for a symmetric (and uncorrelated) initial distribution:

$$\langle y \rangle = R_{34}DYP + T_{344}DYP^2 + U_{3444}DYP(\sigma_{y'}^2 + DYP^2) + o(3) \quad (12)$$

In our case $R_{34} = 0$, $T_{344} = 0$, $U_{3444} = 13$ m, $\sigma_{y'} = 9$ mrad. We obtain then $\langle y \rangle = 1 \mu\text{m}$ for $DYP=1$ mrad and $\langle y \rangle=7 \mu\text{m}$ for $DYP=5$ mrad, which is coherent with what we observe. Another consequence is that this effect scales with the square of the initial angular divergence. Any reduction of the initial beam divergence will significantly reduce the sensitivity of the final vertical beam position to any angular offset. The initial position variation should be below $10 \mu\text{m}$ and the initial angular variation below 5 mrad to keep a final position offset below $10 \mu\text{m}$. The variation with DE is weak because the initial energy spread is very large. The consequence is that with the collimator the same energy range is always selected, which reduces the sensitivity to this offset. In other terms, this offset is negligible in comparison with the initial energy width.

Figure 11: Variations of the beam centroid ($\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle, \langle t \rangle$) (top) and of the beam sizes ($w_x, w_y, \Delta t_{70}$) (bottom) as a function of the initial beam offset positions DX/DY, angles DXP/DYP or relative energy difference DE.

3.2 MAGNET ERRORS

Since the number of magnets is quite low, the study has firstly considered the contribution of each magnet error (misalignment or field) independently from the others. The aim was to get a first estimate of the required tolerances. The second step will be to generate a set of tolerances, to be validated by a mechanical team, and to make Monte Carlo studies. Correction schemes will be identified and studied after diagnostics location is fixed. Special care will be taken to differentiate static errors (the characteristic time of variation is great compared to repetition time: one minute here) and dynamic errors (which vary with a period smaller than repetition time). Static errors can be corrected with a correction scheme, contrary to dynamic ones. The aim here is to have a first guess of the tolerances for the dynamic errors. Misalignment errors are respectively varied for the dipoles/quadrupoles in the range of $\pm 1 \text{ mm}/\pm 0.1 \text{ mm}$ in the transverse direction and $\pm 10 \text{ mm}$ in the longitudinal direction. The roll error is varied in the range $\pm 1 \text{ mrad}$. The field error has been considered in the range $\pm 1\%$ for the quadrupoles and $\pm 2\%$ for the dipoles.

3.2.1 Horizontal misalignment DX

We consider here a horizontal misalignment DX for the dipoles of ± 1 mm with a step of 0.1 mm and for the quadrupoles ± 0.1 mm with a step of 0.01 mm. The final variations of $\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle, \langle t \rangle, w_x, w_y, \Delta t_{70}$ are given in Figure 12 for the dipoles and in Figure 13 for the quadrupoles. We can see that the final beam sizes are very sensitive to the misalignment of Q01 and Q02. The change on w_y comes from orbit errors in the strong sextupoles. A solution to mitigate this effect is to decide not to cancel T₃₄₆. The benefit is weaker sextupoles and a smaller value of U₅₆₆₆. The price is a bigger final vertical beam size. More studies are necessary to quantify the impact of one sextupole family against two families now. The horizontal misalignment of D1, D2, D3, and D4 should respectively be below 0.1 mm, 0.9 mm, 0.9 mm, and 0.2 mm. The horizontal misalignment of Q01, Q02, Q03, Q04, Q05, Q06, Q07, Q08, Q09, and Q10 should respectively be below 5 μm , 10 μm , 14 μm , 3 μm , 3 μm , 3 μm , 3 μm , 14 μm , 10 μm , and 5 μm . The values are very low but please keep in mind that is the requirement on dynamic variations and that static errors can be corrected.

Figure 12: Variations of the beam centroid ($\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle, \langle t \rangle$)(top) and of the beam sizes ($w_x, w_y, \Delta t_{70}$) (bottom) as a function of the misalignment error DX in the dipoles.

Figure 13: Variations of the beam centroid ($\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle, \langle t \rangle$) (top) and of the beam sizes ($w_x, w_y, \Delta t_{70}$) (bottom) as a function of the misalignment error DX in the quadrupoles.

3.2.2 Vertical misalignment DY

We consider here a vertical misalignment DY for the dipoles of ± 1 mm with a step of 0.1 mm and for the quadrupoles ± 0.1 mm with a step of 0.01 mm. We obtain then the final variations of $\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle, \langle t \rangle, w_x, w_y, \Delta t_{70}$ in Figure 14 for the dipoles and in Figure 15 for the quadrupoles. We can see that the final beam sizes are very sensitive to the misalignment of Q01, Q02, Q04, Q05, and Q07. Vertical misalignment of D1, D2, D3, and D4 has no impact here because the considered dipole has no fringe field. The vertical misalignment of Q01, Q02, Q03, Q04, Q05, Q06, Q07, Q08, Q09, and Q10 should respectively be below 4 μm , 3 μm , 30 μm , 6 μm , 9 μm , 9 μm , 6 μm , 30 μm , 3 μm , and 4 μm . The values are very low but please keep in mind that is the requirement on dynamic variations. Static errors can be corrected.

Figure 14: Variations of the beam centroid ($\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle, \langle t \rangle$) (top) and of the beam sizes ($w_x, w_y, \Delta t_{70}$) (bottom) as a function of the misalignment error DY in the dipoles.

Figure 15: Variations of the beam centroid ($\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle, \langle t \rangle$) (top) and of the beam sizes ($w_x, w_y, \Delta t_{70}$) (bottom) as a function of the misalignment error DY in the quadrupoles.

3.2.3 Longitudinal misalignment DZ

We consider here a longitudinal misalignment DZ of ± 10 mm with a step of 1 mm. The variations of $\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle, \langle t \rangle, w_x, w_y, \Delta t_{70}$ are given in Figure 16 for the dipoles and in Figure 17 for the quadrupoles. We can see that the final beam sizes are very sensitive to the longitudinal misalignment of Q01, Q02, Q09, and Q10. The bunch length is sensitive to the longitudinal misalignment of Q04, Q05, Q06, and Q07 as expected. The longitudinal misalignment of D1, D2, D3, and D4 should respectively be below 0.07 mm, 3 mm, 3 mm, and 0.06 mm. The horizontal misalignment of Q01, Q02, Q03, Q04, Q05, Q06, Q07, Q08, Q09, and Q10 should respectively be below 3 mm, 3 mm, 10 mm, 4 mm, 4 mm, 4 mm, 4 mm, 10 mm, 3 mm, and 4 mm.

Figure 16: Variations of the beam centroid ($\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle, \langle t \rangle$) (top) and of the beam sizes ($w_x, w_y, \Delta t_{70}$) (bottom) as a function of the misalignment error DZ in the dipoles.

Figure 17: Variations of the beam centroid ($\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle, \langle t \rangle$) (top) and of the beam sizes ($w_x, w_y, \Delta t_{70}$) (bottom) as a function of the misalignment error DZ in the quadrupoles.

3.2.4 Relative field error FSE

We consider here a respective relative field error FSE (fractional strength error) of $\pm 2\%/\pm 1\%$ in the dipoles/quadrupoles with a step of $0.2\%/0.1\%$. We obtain the final variations of $\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle, \langle t \rangle, w_x, w_y, \Delta t_{70}$ in Figure 18 for the dipoles and in Figure 19 for the quadrupoles. We can see that the final beam sizes are very sensitive to the FSE value of D1 (because of dispersive effects), Q02, Q04, Q07, and Q09. The bunch length is sensitive to the FSE value of Q04, Q05, Q06, and Q07. The FSE value of D1, D2, D3, and D4 should respectively be below 0.02% , 0.03% , 0.03% , and 0.03% . Criteria on the beam sizes are needed to give tolerances on the FSE value in the quadrupoles.

Figure 18: Variations of the beam centroid ($\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle, \langle t \rangle$) (top) and of the beam sizes ($w_x, w_y, \Delta t_{70}$) (bottom) as a function of the relative field error FSE in the dipoles.

Figure 19: Variations of the beam centroid ($\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle, \langle t \rangle$) (top) and of the beam sizes ($w_x, w_y, \Delta t_{70}$) (bottom) as a function of the relative field error FSE in the quadrupoles.

3.2.5 Tilt error

We consider here a tilt error of ± 1 mrad with a step of 0.1 mrad. We obtain then the final variations of $\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle, \langle t \rangle, w_x, w_y, \Delta t_{70}$ in Figure 20 for the dipoles and in Figure 21 for the quadrupoles. The tilt error of D1, D2, D3, and D4 should respectively be below 0.04 mrad, 0.6 mrad, 0.6 mrad, and 0.04 mrad. Correction schemes are necessary to correct the beam orbit to relax the constraint on the tilt error. Criteria on the beam sizes are needed to give tolerances on the tilt error in the quadrupoles.

Figure 20: Variations of the beam centroid ($\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle, \langle t \rangle$) (top) and of the beam sizes ($w_x, w_y, \Delta t_{70}$) (bottom) as a function of the tilt error TILT in the dipoles.

Figure 21: Variations of the beam centroid ($\langle x \rangle, \langle y \rangle, \langle t \rangle$) (top) and of the beam sizes ($w_x, w_y, \Delta t_{70}$) (bottom) as a function of the tilt error TILT in the quadrupoles.

3.3 CONCLUSION

The sensitivity of the line with misalignment and beam errors has been evaluated in the case of a single particle and in the case of a more realistic beam. The studies show that the line is very sensitive to errors. In the current study, errors are not corrected, which means that the tolerances concern here errors with a characteristic time which is small compared to the response time of a feedback system. Therefore, systematic errors (coming for instance from misalignment) can be relaxed if a correction scheme is used. Studies have shown that the transverse misalignment of the quadrupoles is the most critical: their misalignment should stay stable from shot to shot in the range of the micrometer. Secondly, tilt errors of the permanent dipoles D1 and D4 should stay in the range of a few tens of microadians. Finally, the field variations in all magnets should stay below 10^{-4} , which can be achieved with standard power supplies.

4. Magnet design

A first design of the magnets in the transfer line has been realized with OPERA [13]. Main effort was focused on the first dipole magnet. Indeed, at the very beginning of the commissioning, the beam energy spectrum from the plasma injector will have to be characterized. An energy spectrometer is thus required. Moreover, such a diagnostic will be very useful for further studies on the optimization of the first plasma injector. Therefore, the first dipole was designed to allow the measurement of an energy spectrum spanning the range from 50 MeV to 2 GeV. Such a dipole was designed and manufactured with a good agreement with simulations as detailed in this section. Secondly, another dipole was designed to allow the measurement of the energy spectrum from 50 MeV to 5 GeV and more. The possibility of using this dipole also for the transfer line has been studied, and results are encouraging. This option will reduce the total cost of the transfer line. Effort was focused on the permanent dipole D1. The permanent quadrupoles have not been designed yet. Nevertheless, the target parameters as given in Table 3 (inner diameter of 10 mm, maximum gradient of 160 T/m) are in the state of the art: gradients up to 600 T/m have already been achieved [14]. The variable permanent quadrupoles QUAPEVA reach gradients up to 200 T/m [15]. In conclusion, the use of permanent quadrupoles for Q1 and Q2 (viz. Q9 and Q10) is not expected to encounter technical challenges.

Currently, two options have been retained for the inner diameter of the beam pipe in the straight section between the main bend dipoles: 30 mm and 40 mm. Moreover, the nominal energy for the beam line was extended to cover the range from 200 MeV to 300 MeV. The impact of larger beam pipe and reference energy has been addressed for the electromagnets (dipole, quadrupole and sextupoles). The aim of the study was to have a first estimation of the feasibility of such magnets and of the cooling needs. If magnets do not need to be cooled, cost will be greatly reduced: no need of a water supply and higher current density can be reached in the coils (no need of cooling pipes).

4.1 PERMANENT DIPOLE MAGNET FOR AN ENERGY SPECTROMETER

Two permanent dipoles have been designed to be used as an energy spectrometer at CILEX [16]. One of the dipoles has already been manufactured and mapped with a 2% agreement of the measured field map with the OPERA simulation. The performance of both dipoles and the possibility to use one of them as the first dipole of the transfer line will be discussed.

4.1.1 H-shaped permanent magnet dipole

Initially, this dipole has been designed as a construction prototype only. However, it is fully operable in the electron spectrometer for CILEX. The use as D1 is studied here. The designed magnet is 100 mm long and has a gap of 10 mm. It is located at 100 mm behind the source (Figure 22). At this position, the magnet will let a laser beam with a divergence of 50 mrad (corresponding to a diameter of 150 mm at 3 m) pass unobstructed.

Figure 22: Schematic of interaction chamber at CILEX with laser envelope shown in red and magnetic dipole shown in blue. Measurement screens and reference electron trajectories are shown as well.

The main idea of using the geometry shown in Figure 23 is the collection of the flux from the surrounding permanent magnets and concentration into the magnet gap. The strength of the magnet built in this way can therefore exceed the residual field (B_r) of the permanent magnet materials and, in principle, reach the saturation field of pole material which can be more than 2 T. This magnet has been realized and the magnetic field has been measured at different transverse positions (see Figure 24) along the longitudinal axis. A good agreement has been obtained between the simulations and the measurements of real magnet.

Figure 23: TOSCA model of magnet yielding 2.092 T peak field value in the gap. The main component of induction field is shown in colour map from blue (lowest value) to red (highest value).

Figure 24 Profiles of the magnetic field component in the y-direction along the horizontal (x, upper plot) and longitudinal z, (lower plot) directions. Each plot shows the profile at the central position (black) and -20mm offset (blue) and +20mm (offset). For each case dots correspond to the measured and curves to the simulated field values. A scaling factor (~ 1 %) is applied to match the measured and simulated field values

ASTRA [17] simulation software has been applied to study the dynamics of different energy electrons through the designed magnet. The considered electron energy range of [56-2350] MeV has been defined as the lowest energy exiting the magnet from the side of the mechanical gap and the highest energy which is measurable out of 50 mrad divergent laser cone. An idealized electron bunch having Gaussian distribution in all sub spaces was assumed in simulations. Parameters used for the initial electron beam used in ASTRA are summed up in Table 5. 3D magnetic field map has been implemented into ASTRA for the correct treatment of fringe field effects. Electron reference trajectories of different energies and corresponding screens (marked as S#) are illustrated in Figure 25. In the same figure, the mid plane magnetic field profile is shown in colour map. In the plot, the screens have identical size to simplify the design.

Table 5: Electron Beam Parameters used in ASTRA.

LPA beam parameter	Value
Charge, pC	10
Energy, MeV	56-2350
Transverse rms size, μm	2.5
Transverse rms divergence, mrad	2

Figure 25: Range of electron trajectories and corresponding screen positions/orientations for energy measurement inside the interaction chamber of CILEX.

The rms energy resolution at various screens and at different energies is plotted in Figure 26 which yields less than 8 % rms value within the whole energy range for 2 mrad divergence of electron beam.

Figure 26: Rms energy resolution estimated at different screens for 2 mrad electron beam divergence. Different colours symbolize the outcome at different screen positions.

To conclude, a 2.1 Tesla permanent magnet dipole has been designed, constructed, measured and characterized as a spectrometer for CILEX. Very good agreement (about 1 %) between predicted and measured magnetic field values has been obtained. A precise electron beam tracking has been done afterwards by plugging the 3D field map of the magnet into ASTRA simulation program. According to tracking results the magnet will enable to measure electrons from 56 MeV to 2.35 GeV with rms resolution of below 10 percent at full energy range.

This dipole bends electrons of 150MeV by 0.464 rad (angle of D1), and if positioned at a distance of 0.7m from the source the outgoing electrons of this energy will follow the reference trajectory of the transfer line. One should note, however, that at this distance from the focal point even a laser cone of 17 mrad (9-m focal length) cannot pass the magnet gap fully unobstructed.

4.1.2 C-shaped permanent magnet dipole

In its final design, the more powerful C-shaped dipole magnet is 250 mm long and has a gap of 17 mm. This gap choice is motivated by the requirement that a laser cone of 50/3 mrad

(corresponding to a diameter of 150 mm at 9 m) can pass the magnet unobstructed if placed with its exit close to the downstream wall of the vacuum chamber, at about 1m from the source (see schematic view of the magnet in the interaction chamber in Figure 27). This magnet will allow to measure up to 4 GeV electrons inside the interaction chamber (Figure 28). Figure 29 plots the bending angle of such a dipole for different energies. Such a magnet can serve as the first dipole of the dogleg to transport 300 MeV electrons (25.5 degrees bending angle) to the second stage acceleration.

Figure 27: C-shaped magnet inside the interaction chamber.

Figure 28: C-shaped magnet laterally shifted by 35 mm and corresponding trajectories inside interaction chamber. Up to 4 GeV electrons are measurable inside the chamber.

Figure 29: Bending angle as function of energy for the C-shaped magnet.

A design of a 1.6 Tesla, 250 mm long, C-shaped permanent magnet dipole was done. It should allow measurements of up to 4 GeV electrons inside the interaction chamber. The setup will also allow to improve the energy resolution by adding a focusing element in front of the magnet. Full technical specifications of the designed magnet have been sent to SIGMAPHI, and a slightly revised version is currently being manufactured (expected delivery november 2018). The magnet can serve as the first dipole of the dogleg which was designed to transport the beam for the second stage acceleration studies.

4.2 ELECTROMAGNETS

The feasibility of the electromagnets has been addressed. Two extreme cases were considered: an inner diameter of 30 mm and a reference energy of 200 MeV and an inner diameter of 40 mm and a reference energy of 300 MeV. The case of 200 MeV and an inner diameter of 30 mm is the least demanding in terms of magnets. Nevertheless, the drawback of a small diameter of the beam pipe is the acceptance of the transfer line: to transport the beam up to the second stage can be challenging if errors are too large. Moreover, space charge effects at 200 MeV may not be negligible. That is why the second case of an inner diameter of 40 mm and a reference energy of 300 MeV was considered. This case is more demanding in terms of magnets: the required fields are 50% larger on the axis and the pole fields are enlarged more because of a larger diameter. On the other side, the line acceptance is larger and space charge effects are much lower.

4.2.1 Inner radius of 30 mm and a reference energy of 200 MeV

The field maps in the electromagnet dipole, quadrupole, and in the sextupole are respectively given in Figure 30, Figure 31, and Figure 32. The magnets are designed to get the target values given in Table 2, Table 3, and

Table 4: peak field of 0.22 T in the dipole, peak gradient of 20 T/m in the quadrupole, and peak gradient of 152 T/m² in the sextupole. The results show that target values can be reached far from the saturation field in the iron. The power dissipated by Joule effect in the dipoles (60 W per coil), in the quadrupoles (20 W per coil), and in the sextupoles (less than 0.5 W per coil) are low enough to avoid water cooling. To conclude, studies show that such magnets are feasible with no showstopper.

Figure 30: OPERA model of a dipole yielding 0.22 T peak field value in the gap of 30 mm. The current density in the coils is 3 A/mm² for a total of 2700 A.turn. The dissipated power by the Joule effect is 60 W per coil. The main component of induction field is shown left in colour map from blue (lowest value) to red (highest value). The variation of the magnetic field at the middle of the dipole along the horizontal axis is plotted on the right.

Figure 31: OPERA model of a quadrupole yielding 22 T/m peak gradient value for an inner diameter of 30 mm. The current density in the coils is 1.5 A/mm² for a total of 2060 A.turn. The dissipated power by the Joule effect is 20 W per coil. The main component of induction field is shown left in colour map from blue (lowest value) to red (highest value). The variation of the quadrupole gradient along the horizontal axis is plotted on the right.

Figure 32: OPERA model of a sextupole yielding 152 T/m² peak gradient value for an inner diameter of 30 mm. The current density in the coils is 0.5 A/mm² for a total of 135 A.turn. The dissipated power by the Joule effect is less than 0.5 W per coil. The main component of induction field is shown left in colour map from blue (lowest value) to red (highest value). The variation of the sextupole gradient along the horizontal axis is plotted on the right.

4.2.2 Inner radius of 40 mm and a reference energy of 300 MeV

The field maps in the electromagnet dipole, quadrupole, and in the sextupole are respectively given in Figure 33, Figure 34, and Figure 35. The magnets are designed to get the target values given in Table 2, Table 3, and

Table 4: peak field of 0.33 T in the dipole, peak gradient of 30 T/m in the quadrupole, and peak gradient of 228 T/m² in the sextupole. Results show that target values can be reached far from the saturation field in the iron for the sextupole and the dipole. Nevertheless, studies show that the saturation field of 1.65 T is reached for the quadrupole. Moreover, calculations were performed with a 2D model. In future 3D calculations we expect a somewhat lower value with the consequence that the desired gradient integral may not be reached. Therefore, longer quadrupoles are should be used to reduce the peak field and to get margin on the gradient integral. The power dissipated by Joule effect in the dipoles (280 W per coil), in the quadrupoles (140 W per coil), and in the sextupoles (4 W per coil) becomes larger but remains manageable without hollow conductor cooling. To conclude, some optimisation is still necessary for the quadrupole but the magnets appear still feasible. Nevertheless, an inner diameter of 40 mm and a reference energy of 300 MeV seem to be near the limit of what can be done. Beyond these values, magnet power consumption are likely to motivate the use of pulsed power supply, and second iteration is expected to be necessary to avoid field saturation in the iron.

Figure 33: OPERA model of magnet yielding 0.33 T peak field value in the gap of 40 mm. The current density in the coils is 6 A/mm² for a total of 5400 A.turn. The dissipated power by the Joule effect is 280 W per coil. The main component of induction field is shown left in colour map from blue (lowest value) to red (highest value). The variation of the magnetic field at the middle of the dipole along the horizontal axis is plotted on the right.

Figure 34: OPERA model of a quadrupole yielding 33 T/m peak gradient value for an inner diameter of 40 mm. The current density in the coils is 2.8 A/mm² for a total of 5600 A.turn. The dissipated power by the Joule effect is 140 W per coil. The main component of induction field is shown left in colour map from blue (lowest value) to red (highest value). The variation of the quadrupole gradient along the horizontal axis is plotted on the right.

Figure 35: OPERA model of a sextupole yielding 225 T/m² peak gradient value for an inner diameter of 40 mm. The current density in the coils is 1 A/mm² for a total of 480 A.turn. The dissipated power by the Joule effect is less than 4 W per coil. The main component of induction field is shown left in colour map from blue (lowest value) to red (highest value). The variation of the sextupole gradient along the horizontal axis is plotted on the right.

5. Future plans

The optics design of the dogleg has been described. The beam can be transported with feasible values in the magnets. Final performances of the transfer line are very dependent on the initial beam distribution. Collimation is needed to clean the beam in energy and in angle. Any improvement of the plasma injector will have a big impact on the final properties. It is obvious, that optimisation should aim at reducing the energy spread but also the beam divergence. Indeed, emittance growth quadratically depends on these two parameters. The future plan is to undertake more plasma simulation to get a better initial distribution. Otherwise, collimation can clean the beam to get a quite low final emittance. The price is a reduction of the final charge. A trade-off must be found between cleaning the tails and sufficient charge to be measured at diagnostics. Optics of the transfer line should be modified accordingly to the advances on the magnetic design. For instance, field maps of the dipoles should be integrated into tracking studies. When matching conditions are defined for the second laser-plasma acceleration stage, optics will be modified to get the final required beam sizes.

Studies on the line tolerances are very preliminary. Next steps are to converge to realistic values on the dynamic range of the misalignment and field errors. Then, Monte Carlo studies will be undertaken to get the expected uncertainty on the beam properties (centroid and sizes) at different locations, corresponding to diagnostics locations or second stage entrance. Correction schemes will be developed to correct static errors and to define the tolerances to pilot the magnets (like tolerance on the integrated field).

Magnetic design of the permanent dipoles (2D and 3D simulations) and of all electromagnets (only 2D simulations) exist. If a diameter of 30 mm is chosen for the beam pipe diameter, magnets are feasible with no showstopper. Cooling is not necessary. If a diameter of 40 mm and a reference energy of 300 MeV are chosen, sextupoles and dipoles are feasible but magnetic field saturates into the iron of the quadrupole. Quadrupoles should be then longer. Next step is to freeze the inner diameter of the beam pipe. The magnetic design will be then optimized and electromagnets will be ordered. One permanent dipole has already been ordered and should be delivered end 2018. The dipole will be then measured and the obtained field map will be used to refine the optics design of the line. Requiring non-realistic magnets is one of the risks of the transfer line. The magnetic design of the permanent dipoles and of the electromagnets has shown that these magnets are feasible. Nevertheless, the magnetic design of the permanent quadrupoles has not been addressed yet. The required gradient is less than 150 T/m which is within the state of the art: variable permanent quadrupoles have achieved gradients up to 200 T/m. Next step will be to optimize the magnetic design of the permanent quadrupoles and to check their feasibility.

A comparison of the different methods to characterize the beam (charge, beam position, transverse and longitudinal beam profile, and emittance) has started. A table will be compiled which sums up the selected diagnostics at different stages of the commissioning as well as their location and quantity. The next step is to finalize the mechanical design and the cost estimate of the budget. A commissioning strategy jointly with beam dynamics studies is to be undertaken to validate the baseline. The commissioning strategy will foresee different stages and be finalized middle 2019 to be ready to start the commissioning early 2020 as specified.

6. References

- [1] B. Cros, B.S. Paradkar, X. Davoine, A. Chancé, F.G. Desforges, S. Dobosz-Dufrénoy, N. Delerue, J. Ju, T.L. Audet, G. Maynard, M. Lobet, L. Gremillet, P. Mora, J. Schwindling, O. Delferrière, C. Bruni, C. Rimbault, T. Vinatier, A. Di Piazza, M. Grech, C. Riconda, J.R. Marquès, A. Beck, A. Specka, Ph. Martin, P. Monot, D. Normand, F. Mathieu, P. Audebert, F. Amiranoff, “Laser plasma acceleration of electrons with multi-PW laser beams in the frame of CILEX,” *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A*, pp. 27-33, 2014.
- [2] “MAD-X website,” [Online]. Available: <http://cern.ch/mad>.
- [3] “TraceWin website,” [Online]. Available: <http://irfu.cea.fr/dacm/logiciels/>.
- [4] M. Borland, “elegant: A Flexible SDDS-Compliant Code for Accelerator Simulation,” Advanced Photon Source LS-287, 2000.
- [5] S. Fartoukh, *Méthodes d'analyse d'une ligne de focalisation finale dans le cadre du projet du collisionneur linéaire TESLA*, PhD thesis, 1997, p. 118.
- [6] P. Lee, G. Maynard, T. L. Audet, B. Cros, R. Lehe and J.-L. Vay, *Phys. Rev. ST Accel. Beams*, vol. 21, p. 052802, 2018.
- [7] M. Migliorati, A. Bacci, C. Benedetti, E. Chiadroni, M. Ferrario, A. Mostacci, L. Palumbo, A. R. Rossi, L. Serafini and P. Antici, *Phys. Rev. ST Accel. Beams*, vol. 16, p. 011302, 2013.
- [8] M. Scisciò, L. Lancia, M. Migliorati, A. Mostacci, L. Palumbo, Y. Papaphilippou and P. Antici, *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 119, p. 094905, 2016.
- [9] B. Marchetti, R. Aßmann, S. Baark, U. Dorda, C. Engling, K. Flöttmann, M. Werner, C. Wiebers, L. Winkelmann, K. Wittenburg and J. Zhu, “Status Update of the SINBAD-ARES Linac Under Construction at DESY,” in *8th International Particle Accelerator Conference*, Copenhagen (Denmark), 2017.
- [10] J. Derouillat, A. Beck, F. Pérez, T. Vinci, M. Chiaramello, A. Grassi, M. Flé, G. Bouchard, I. Plotnikov, N. Aunai, J. Dargent, C. Riconda and M. Grech, “SMILEI: a collaborative, open-source, multi-purpose particle-in-cell code for plasma simulation,” *Comput. Phys. Commun.*, vol. 222, pp. 351-373, 2018.
- [11] K. Floettmann, *Phys. Rev. ST Accel. Beams*, vol. 17, p. 054402, 2014.

- [12] X. Li, A. Mosnier and P. A. P. Nghiem, “Design of a 5 GeV laser–plasma accelerating module in the quasi-linear regime,” *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A*, p. in press, 2018.
- [13] “OPERA website,” [Online]. Available: <https://operafea.com>.
- [14] J. K. Lim, P. Frigola, G. Travish, J. B. Rosenzweig, S. G. Anderson, W. J. Brown, J. S. Jacob, C. L. Robbins and A. M. Tremaine, “Adjustable, short focal length permanent-magnet quadrupole based electron beam final focus system,” *Phys. Rev. ST Accel Beams*, vol. 8, p. 072401, 2005.
- [15] F. Marteau, P. N'Gotta, C. Benabderrahmane, A. Ghaith, M. Valléau, A. Loulergue, J. Vétéran, M. Sebdaoui, T. André, G. L. Bec, J. Chavanne, C. Vallerand, D. Oumbarek, O. Cosson, F. Forest, P. Jivkov, J. Lancelot and M. Couprie, “Variable high gradient permanent magnet quadrupole (QUAPEVA),” *Appl.Phys.Lett.*, vol. 111, p. 253503, 2017.
- [16] M. Khojayan, A. Cauchois, J. Prudent and A. Specka, “Design of a Compact Permanent Magnet Spectrometer for CILEX/APOLLON,” in *IBIC2018*, 2018.
- [17] K. Floettmann, “ASTRA website,” [Online]. Available: <http://www.desy.de/~mpyflo/>.

Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
ICT	Integrated Current Transformers
BPM	Beam Position Monitor
OTR	Optical Transition Radiation
YAG	Yttrium Aluminium Garnet
X	coordinate vector $(x, x', y, y', l, \delta)$
R_{ij}	First derivative of the final coordinate $X_{1,i}$ with the initial coordinate $X_{0,j}$
T_{ijk}	Second derivative of the final coordinate $X_{1,i}$ with the initial coordinates $X_{0,j}$ and $X_{0,k}$
rms	Root mean square
$\langle x \rangle$	Mean value of x
TBD	To be defined
RF	Radio-frequency